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Review Article

**A FAMILY MEDICINE PRACTICE, ESTIMATING THE
PREVALENCE OF OSTEOPENIA / OSTEOPOROSIS IN
PATIENTS HAVING LIVER CIRRHOSIS IN KSA****¹Majed Fahad Al-Sharari, ²Ala Musa Al-Ghthy, ³Norah Abdulrahman AlFuraydi, ⁴Hatim Abdulali Alshaikh, ⁵Ohood Ayed Allogmani, ⁶Hind Mohammad Armit Alsulami, ⁷Wejdan Jumyaan Alharbi, ⁸Abdulmajeed Fahad Alahmari, ⁹Afraha Dhaifallah Alanazi****¹Tabuk University, ²Tabuk University, ³King Abdulaziz University, ⁴Umm al Qura University, ⁵Ibn Sina College, ⁶Umm Al-Qura University, ⁷King Abdulaziz University, ⁸Ibn Sina College, ⁹Tabuk University****Abstract:**

Introduction: Osteoporosis is a common age-related disorder manifested clinically by skeletal fractures, especially fractures of the vertebrae, hip, and distal forearm. The major cause of these fractures is low bone mass, although an increase in trauma due to falls in the elderly also contributes. **Objective:** To assess the frequency of liver cirrhosis patients complaining of osteoporosis in family medicine department. **Methods and place:** The data of this cross-sectional study was collected from different hospitals in KSA from the period of January 2017 to March 2018. The patients' age group 36-80 years suffering from liver cirrhosis for at least 2 years or more were enrolled. The detailed clinical and socio-demographic data was collected and analyzed by Spss 21. The patient was labeled positive for osteoporosis when the T score recorded was less than 2.5 on DEXA scans. **Results:** A total of 300 cases were enrolled, out of them 140 (54%) males and 160 (66%) were females with mean age of 55.47±8.13 years. Osteoporosis was recorded in 101 (44%) of patients. Osteoporosis affects females more, where it is seen in 60 (52.23%) out of 160 cases with p= 0.06.

Osteoporosis has significantly high prevalence (p=0.003) in patients suffering from cirrhosis for more than 4 years affecting 66 (57.94%) cases in contrast to 22 (21%) cases in their same groups. And the percentage is not related to a specific type of hepatitis. **Conclusion:** Osteoporosis/ Osteopenia undoubtedly is common in cases of liver cirrhosis significantly increasing the morbidity and mortality for the patients. Almost every 4th person suffering from hepatic cirrhosis suffers from osteoporosis and the prevalence peaks as the duration of disease increases.

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INTRODUCTION:

Osteoporosis is a common age-related disorder manifested clinically by skeletal fractures, especially fractures of the vertebrae, hip, and distal forearm.² The major cause of these fractures is low bone mass, although an increase in trauma due to falls in the elderly also contributes. There are multiple causes for the low bone mass which, in any given individual, may contribute differently to the development of the osteopenia.⁵ The most important groups of causes are failure to achieve adequate peak bone mass, slow bone loss due to processes relating to aging, the menopause in women, and a variety of sporadic behavioral, nutritional, and environmental factors that affect bone mass in some but not in other individuals. The most important approach is prevention.⁷ Drugs and behavioral factors known to cause bone loss should be eliminated and perimenopausal women should be evaluated for possible preventive administration of estrogen. For patients with fractures due to established osteoporosis, the only drugs approved by the Food and Drug Administration are the antiresorptive agents calcium, estrogen, and calcitonin. Formation-stimulating regimens, however, are being developed and may be available for clinical use in the foreseeable future.⁹ These regimens may be capable of increasing bone mass to above the fracture threshold, thereby resulting in a clinical cure of the osteoporosis.

OBJECTIVE

The main objective is to define the prevalence of osteoporosis/osteopenia in patients complaining from liver cirrhosis.

In this article, it is recorded that the cases with chronic liver disease suffer from bone mass loss at quite a faster rate than the normal individuals.

It has been recorded that age, gender, and the degree of liver cirrhosis were important risk factors for development of osteopenia and osteoporosis in patients suffering from primary sclerosing cholangitis.^[8] The best strategy to manage the osteoporosis in patients with cirrhosis is the primary prevention, the focus of our study is to identify the important risk factors of osteoporosis in patients of liver cirrhosis so that the burden of fractures secondary to osteoporosis can be decreased.^[33,34]

The decrease in bone mass density can result in complications like easy fractures.^[33] The estimated prevalence for liver-related osteoporosis is between 30-340/100000 of the general population.^[3] Other risk factors like decreased sun exposure, female gender, smoking history, steroid use, diabetes mellitus, alcoholism etc also predispose to osteoporosis.^[4]

Furthermore different pathogenic mediators like fibronectin, insulin like growth factor-I, and various cytokines involved in progression of the disease have also been recognized.^[29] Isolated liver disease to be the cause of osteoporosis in the absence of these cofactors, osteoporosis due to liver cirrhosis is a neglected and highly under rated entity.^[29]

However, despite the pathogenesis of osteopenia is highlighted by the advancement of bone biology, the treatment options for this disease remains unchanged i.e. supplementation with calcium, vitamin D and use of bisphosphonates.^[36]

Various studies have been conducted on this topic and different modalities of investigations have been used. In our study we used mono energy x-rays absorptiometry (DEXA) scan to assess the bone density.^[31] The bone mass depends upon the harmony and the balance between two opposite processes: bone formation by the osteoblasts and bone resorption by osteoclasts. ^[32,33] As a result, the resorption exceeds the bone formation level, this results in osteopenia and bone loss.^[25,32,33] The mechanisms of osteoporosis in liver diseases are not completely understood. Some studies suggest increased bone resorption while some indicate decreased bone formation due to impairment of the osteoblastic activity resulting in decreased bone wall thickness and defective matrix.^[30]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is a cross sectional study, data were collected from different hospitals in KSA, from the period of January 2017 to March 2018.

The 300 patients were enrolled in this study with age ranging 36-80 years, diagnosed cases of liver cirrhosis (diagnosed radiologically with shrunken liver, clinically with presence of jaundice, ascities or any other sign of chronic liver disease with increased prothrombin time and decreased albumin).

Inclusion criteria: 1. patients in age group 36-80 years. 2. diagnosed as a case of liver cirrhosis due to hep B or hep C for more than 2 year.

Exclusion criteria: patients who had co-morbidities like diabetes mellitus, heart diseases, end stage renal diseases and metabolic disorders.

The social and demographic data is collected in detail with the help of preformed questionnaires. The data is recorded and analyzed with spss21.

The age, duration of disease etc were recorded as mean and qualitative data like gender and presence of osteoporosis was recorded as median, stratification of

the effect modifiers was done and post stratification chi square was applied.

The patients whose had DEXA scan result was less than 2.5 were labelled as osteoporotic.

RESULTS:

In this study, there were total of 300 cases out of them ,140 (54%) males and 160 (66%) were females with mean age of 55.47±8.13 years. Osteoporosis

was recorded in 101 (44%) of patients. Osteoporosis affects females more, where it is seen in 60 (52.23%) out of 160 cases with p= 0.06.

Osteoporosis has significantly high prevalence (p=0.003) in patients suffering from cirrhosis for more than 4 year affecting 66 (57.94%) cases in contrast to 22 (21%) cases in their same groups. And the percentage is not related to a specific type of hepatitis.

type	Osteoporosis (yes)	Osteoporosis (no)
Hepatitis B	23%	72%
Hepatitis C	45%	35%

DISCUSSION:

Liver cirrhosis is a major health concern across the world and it is a cause of great burden on health providing institutions in the developing countries and countries of middle east.

Taking in the account of pathophysiology and functions of liver that involve various mechanisms, the patients of liver cirrhosis are more susceptible to develop osteoporosis due to decrease bone mineral density and impaired osteoblastic activity.[4,7,2]

The prevalence of osteoporosis CLD patients was recorded to be in 14% to 55% cases in western world.[15–17] In our study, the prevalence of osteoporosis in liver cirrhosis was reported to be 54% in patients with liver cirrhosis that was caused by viral infections of hep b and hep C. The results in

comparison to other studies show wide variability of recorded prevalence of osteoporosis that maybe due to different age group, etiologies and disease duration of the patients.[6,18] In this study, the patients of liver cirrhosis due to autoimmune hepatitis were excluded as that may have developed osteoporosis due to glucocorticoid consumption.

This is one of the reason that why the reported prevalence of the disease in our study is relatively lower. However, this value is not significant statistically. osteoporosis is quite high in patients suffering from liver cirrhosis for more than 4 years. i.e(56.36%) Liver plays vital role in regulation of bone metabolism.[19] Hypogonadism is an important risk factor for osteopenia and osteoporosis, thus, CLD would accelerate the development of hypogonadism in the patients due to imbalance between the gonadotrophic hormones as a result of

poor metabolic functions of the liver [19] Furthermore, a reduced level of circulating estrogen in the body may be another mediator to produce osteopenia and osteoporosis.[20]

The prevalence of Osteoporosis was high in those cases who suffered from cirrhosis for more than 3 years affecting 120 (36.66%) patients in contrast to 42 (21%) of patients who suffered for less than 3 years duration. The results of our study is comparable to studies done in the past by Javed et al.13 and Sokhi et al. 7 , their results showed a positive correlation in between duration of hepatic cirrhosis and risk of osteoporosis.[7,13]

Vitamin D3 plays pivotal role in normal homeostasis of serum calcium and bone matrix.[22]The serum level of D3 is altered in patients of liver cirrhosis. Vitamin D is either absorbed through the gut or synthesized in the skin , tan is then hydroxylated in the liver by enzyme 25-alpha-hydroxylase and then in kidney by 1-alpha-hydroxylase, then active metabolite 1,25-alpha-hydroxylase is formed.[21] Patients who suffer from cirrhosis often have low vitamin D3 levels.[22]

The results of our study show that the females after menopause are more susceptible to develop osteoporosis due to change in hormonal balance. Low BMI is also associated with increased risk of osteoporosis in patients with PBC.[28]

Another study done shows that weight loss is related to general increased risk of fractures and weight gain has association with reduced hip fracture risks.[26,27]

Low BMI was another risk factor associated with osteoporosis ,Consistently, the results of our study implies that patients with noncholestatic liver cirrhosis with lower BMI are more prone to develop osteoporosis.[33,34]

Although a lot of studies done report the relationship between the Child–Pugh score and decreased bone mass, conflicting findings still exist. As there are a number of accompanying conditions in decompensated liver cirrhosis patients , including elevated prothrombin time,bilirubin and ascites. [35]The symptoms like ascites may affect the assessment of patients weight and BMD,hence,in our study all the enrolled patients were child pugh score A. The symptoms such as ascites would affect the patients' weight and BMD assessment. Hence, in this study, all included patients are compensated cirrhosis patients with liver function being Child–Pugh A.

The results of our study may be different from the other studies done in the other parts of the world as it is highly heterogenous topic, the sample size,age group of the patients,disease duration of the patients and child-pugh scoring may differ,consequently,results are altered.

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